

FLUORIDE CATALYZED CONVERSION OF β -ACETOXYETHYLSILSESQUIOXANE: CHLORIDE-FREE PRECURSOR FOR SILICA FILMS

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Introduction

The spin-on-glass (SOG) approach to ceramic films involves coating a surface with a soluble precursor solution and subsequent thermal conversion to the desired material. The inherent processibility of the precursors makes this approach attractive for gap-filling and planarization applications. Typical SOG precursors are based on sol-gel chemistry, in which hydrolysis of silicon alkoxides produces meta-stable hydroxy-substituted species, which subsequently undergo condensation to a three-dimensional network - i.e. silica or related materials. A significant advantage of sol-gel processing is the relatively low reaction temperatures required compared with other methods.^{1,2} On the other hand, SOG precursors based on sol-gel chemistry usually require highly unstable solutions generated by the hydrolysis of alkoxysilanes, which have limited shelf-life and necessitate removal of large amounts of alcohol and water during curing.

We previously reported a new approach to SOG materials based on "hydrolysis in stages" using β -chloroethylsilsesquioxanes (BCESSQ) as the silica precursor.³ This contribution describes the preparation and processing of a new chloride-free analogue, β -acetoxyethylsilsesquioxane (BAESSQ).

Experimental

All solvents and reagents were used as received without further purification. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA/MS) analyses were performed on a Texas Instrument SDT 2960 simultaneous DTA-TGA with a Fison Thermalab mass spectral analyzer. Ceramic residue yields are reported as the percentage of the sample remaining after completion of the heating cycle. Film compositions were determined by Rutherford backscattering spectrometry (RBS) using 2.0 MeV He⁺ ions for silicon and oxygen, and 3.4 MeV He²⁺ ions for carbon as described previously.⁴ X-ray powder diffraction spectra of the Ormosil products were obtained on a Rigaku Geigerflex powder X-ray diffractometer using Cu K α radiation with a graphite monochromator. AFM images were obtained in tapping mode.

Preparative scale tube furnace pyrolyses were performed in boron nitride or silica boats in a quartz tube wrapped with heating tape (190 °C) or in Lindberg 55035, 54233 and 54434 tube furnaces equipped with Eurotherm temperature controllers (350 and 1200 °C). Thermolyses were performed under a stream of air saturated with water. Samples were dried at 200 °C under flowing dry air or vacuum prior to analysis. Elemental analyses were performed at the Nesmeyanov Institute of Organoelement Compounds (INEOS), Moscow, Russia. NMR analysis was obtained in collaboration with Dow Corning Corp.

Results and Discussion

β -Acetoxyethylsilsesquioxanes were prepared from the triethoxide via conventional hydrolysis routes.^{1,2} The material is a pale-yellow viscous resin. TGA/MS analysis reveals the first major onset of weight loss occurring at ca. 250 °C, which is accompanied by evolution of ethylene and acetic acid.

The products of the bulk thermolysis of β -acetoxyethylsilsesquioxane in a tube furnace at various temperatures were examined by elemental analysis, XRD, and NMR (¹³C, ²⁹Si). The products treated at 350 and 450 °C are orange-brown solids with calculated empirical formulas Si_{1.0}O_{2.2}C_{0.43}H_{1.63} and Si_{1.0}O_{2.1}C_{0.34}H_{1.0}, respectively. The residual carbon is mostly methyl and vinyl groups suggesting the following mechanism shown in Figure 1. The evolution of ethylene and acetic acid observed in the TGA/MS further supports the proposed mechanism.

Figure 1. Proposed mechanism for uncatalyzed thermal conversion of BAESSQ.

A sample of BASSQ heated to 1200 °C for 2 hours resulted in a black residue that is amorphous (XRD). This is fully consistent with conversion of a silica containing some organic groups to silicon oxycarbide or "black glass", the well-known product of organosilsesquioxane pyrolysis.^{5,6}

Although residual organic carbon is not inherently detrimental for all potential applications, greater control over the thermal conversion process was desired. Thus, catalysts for the BAE decomposition were explored. Addition of 5 mol % tetrabutylammonium fluoride (TBAF) to BAESSQ results in a striking change in the thermal behavior observed in the TGA/MS (Figure 2). Some initial weight loss is associated with residual water and solvent introduced with the TBAF. However, ethylene and acetic acid evolution is rapid starting ca. 100 °C. As the temperature approaches 200 °C, weight loss accelerates, and a new species, butene, is observed in the MS. Butene is the most volatile product of the known decomposition of TBAF. The mass (54%) is fairly constant up to 300 °C, at which point another burst of ethylene and acetic acid is observed. These results suggest the following: (1) TBAF is an effective catalyst for the conversion of BAE groups <200 °C; (2) TBAF decomposes rapidly at 200 °C; and (3) any BAE groups remaining after catalyst decomposition undergo uncatalyzed conversion >250 °C. The obvious implications are that processing temperatures below the TBAF decomposition threshold will be most effective, and TBAF can be subsequently removed by heating >200 °C.

Figure 2. TGA/MS of BAE resin with 5% TBAF.

This was confirmed by TGA/MS, in which the temperature was raised to 190 °C and held for 2.5 hours, then raised to 350 °C. Ethylene and acetic acid evolve rapidly, but only small amounts of butene are released, suggesting the TBAF is largely intact. However, as soon as the temperature is raised above 200 °C, butene is observed, along with rather small amounts of the other gases. The latter may be due to gases trapped in the sample that are released when the temperature is raised. Following the treatment at 350 °C for 1.5 hours, the ceramic yield is 46%, and more significantly, the resulting product is white.

Bulk pyrolysis of 3 BAESSQ samples with 5% TBAF was performed under conditions suggested by the TGA-MS studies. The first sample was heated only at 170 °C for 3 h. The second was heated for 2.5 h at 190 °C and then 1.5 h at 350 °C, while the third was treated identically to the second, but subsequently heated at 1200 °C for 2 h. The resultant solids from all three experiments were colorless, and the elemental analyses

reveal dramatically lower levels of carbon and hydrogen than in those processed without the catalyst (Table I). The sample heated to 350 °C contains < 1% carbon, and significantly, 1.5% fluorine. Furthermore, the sample heated to 1200 °C contains no detectable carbon, and now exhibits substantial crystallinity in the XRD, matching the pattern for silica in the cristobalite form. Fluoride has previously been shown to promote condensation and crystallization in sol-gel derived silica.⁷

Table I: Composition of BAESSQ processed with 5% TBAF catalyst.

Processing Temp (°C)	%C	%H	%Si	%O ^a
190, 350	0.91	0.91	43.56	53.07
190, 350, 1200	-	-	48.00	52.00

^a % oxygen calculated by difference

The CP-MAS ²⁹Si NMR of Sample 1 (170 °C) reveals > 85% of the silicon centers are Q-type sites, with Q⁺ predominating. The region between -60 and -70 ppm, indicative of T-groups, is much smaller - ca. 14% - than in the uncatalyzed samples. Because cross-polarization causes the large Q⁺ peak to be underestimated, the relative area of the T-region may be overestimated by as much as a factor of 2.

The CP-MAS/TOSS ¹³C NMR spectrum of Sample 1 is quite interesting. Again, the peak at δ 170 is due to a carbonyl, presumably acetate, and the associated methyl should be in the region of ca. δ 20. However, it is clear that the majority of this acetate is not due to unreacted BAE groups, as the characteristic Si-CH₃ (δ 6.9) and O-CH₃ (δ 54) are very small at best. The remaining peaks are consistent with butyl ammonium species. Thus, δ 60 would correspond to N-CH₂ groups (e.g. δ 58-61 in the solution spectra of TBA salts), and the δ 14 corresponds well to the terminal methyl on a butyl group (e.g. δ 12-17 in the solution spectra of TBA salts). The remaining two methylene groups are expected to fall in the range of δ 20-25, coincident with the possible acetate methyl. One difficulty with this spectrum is in identifying the carbons that should be bound to the silicon, corresponding to the ca. 14% T-groups observed in the ²⁹Si NMR of this sample. Methyl groups directly bound to silicon are generally found upfield of δ 0, and methylenes attached to silicon are generally upfield of δ 10. However, no significant peaks are found upfield of δ 11 in the ¹³C NMR of the sample. It is clear, however, that N-butyl groups are present, as expected for a sample not heated above ca. 200 °C. In addition, no vinyl groups are observed.

The CP-MAS ²⁹Si NMR spectrum of Sample 2 (190/350 °C) reveals approximately 90% of the silicon centers as Q-type, with Q⁺ and Q⁺ predominating. In addition, a small resonance is observed at δ -80 (ca. 3%), a region not generally associated with either T- or Q-groups. It is possible that this resonance is due to fluoride-substituted silicon centers (i.e., FSiO_{1.5}), although five-coordinate fluorosilicates generally are found upfield of δ -100.⁸

Given the low concentration of T-groups in the Ormosil heated to 350 °C, it is not surprising that it was considerably more difficult to obtain the ¹³C (CP-MAS) NMR spectrum (Figure 21). Small peaks are found in four main regions of the spectrum. Signals at δ 160 - 180 are probably due to acetate carbonyls, and peaks between δ 120 - 140 are likely vinylic carbons.³⁰ Although many small peaks are found throughout the aliphatic region, it is very significant that no resonances are observed upfield of 0 ppm, in the region associated with Si-CH₃ groups. Additionally, many small peaks are found between δ 50 - 100, suggesting carbons bound to oxygen (C-OR), or nitrogen (C-NR₂), or possibly alkynyl carbons. These organic residues may arise from pyrolyses of the T-groups or acetate and N-butyl residues described above in Sample 1 (170 °C). Again, all the peaks observed in the ¹³C NMR spectrum constitute a relatively small percentage of the total Ormosil (0.91 wt% by elemental analysis).

Experiments confirm that BAESSQ can be used as a SOG to prepare films. Solutions of BAESSQ in diglyme (1 - 40 wt%) were deposited on silicon substrates by spin-coating to yield as-cast films ranging in thickness from 200 - 6000 Å. Processing at 350 or 450 °C for 4 hours resulted in ca. 50% decrease in thickness, although there was little change after 20 min. Analysis of the films by AFM and SEM reveals extremely smooth, featureless surfaces (RMS roughness ~ 0.35 nm). Film compositions (RBS) correlate closely to the elemental analysis measured for the bulk samples.

Fluoride successfully catalyzed the thermal conversion of BAESSQ to silica in the bulk, therefore a similar process was investigated in thin films. A 6100 Å film was prepared from a diglyme solution of BAESSQ and 10 wt% TBAF, and the film was heated to 160 °C for 3 h. The thickness decreased to 54 and the refractive index decreased from 1.47 to 1.30. Furthermore, the FTIR spectrum resembles that of a film converted at 350 °C without a catalyst. Most notably, the carbonyl band of the acetate group has virtually disappeared. For purposes of comparison, a parallel study was conducted with a film containing *no* fluoride. In sharp contrast, the thickness of this control film only dropped to 84%, the refractive index increased to 1.55, and most significantly, the FTIR spectrum is virtually indistinguishable from that of an as-deposited BAESSQ film. Specifically, the carbonyl, C-H, and Si-C bands are undiminished. The spectrum suggests there has been no significant chemical change in the film, and the thickness and refractive index values indicate there has been slight densification and/or solvent loss. Indeed, ellipsometry measurements reveal that the thickness of a freshly spin-coated film decreases by 7-10% after 15 h *in vacuo* at 25 °C. Thus, it is not unreasonable that 16% loss in thickness is observed after 3 h at 160 °C without significant conversion of the BAESSQ sample.

The fluoride-containing film was subsequently heated to 350 °C for 1.5 h. The thickness decreased to 44%, and the FTIR reveals total disappearance of the carbonyl stretch and the C-H vibrations. In the case of the control film (no TBAF), heating at 350 °C led to a major drop in thickness from 84% to 44, and the refractive index decreased to 1.32 both are indicative of BAESSQ conversion in films. The FTIR spectrum now reveals complete loss of the carbonyl band, as is observed in the case of the films prepared with TBAF. The C-H stretches, although much smaller, are still observable.

RBS was used to determine the elemental composition of films processed with TBAF and the controls. Surprisingly, the carbon levels are nearly identical in the catalyzed film (14 atom% C) and the control (13 atom% C) following processing at 350 °C. This is in stark contrast to the bulk studies, in which treatment of a catalyzed sample at 350 °C resulted in only 1.3 atom% residual carbon, whereas 8.1 atom% carbon was found in bulk samples processed without TBAF.

CONCLUSIONS

β -Acetoxyethylsilsequioxane (BAESSQ) is a soluble resin that undergoes conversion to silica-rich materials in bulk or thin films under relatively mild thermal conditions. Onset of thermal conversion occurs above 250 °C, but results in ~10% residual carbon as organic SSQ sites. The thermal conversion of BAESSQ is dramatically accelerated in the presence of TBAF, allowing processing <200 °C and yielding a silica with <1% carbon, which does not appear to be covalently bound to silicon. It has been shown that BAESSQ is a chloride-free route for the production of silica-rich films under mild conditions. Addition of a fluoride catalyst permits conversion of the polymer rapidly at 160 °C. Films heated to 350 °C contain ca. 10 atom% of carbon. The exact nature of the residual carbon remains unclear, but may be SSQ sites or trapped volatile organics which are released upon further heating. Additionally, the films produced have been shown to be extremely smooth and defect free.

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